

Name: Dr. Alex Kim

Gender: Female

Degree: Ph.D. in Computer Science

Position: Cybersecurity Lead

Field of Study: Computer Science with a focus on Cybersecurity

Research Discipline: Network Security, Cryptography

Affiliation: Cybersecurity Research Group, Technical University of Munich

Hair: Medium length, straight, black

Skin: Fair

Fashion Style: Professional, prefers smart-tech wearables for efficiency

Glasses/Contact Lenses: Black-framed glasses

Jewellery: Prefers a smart ring that serves as a security token

Wearables: Smartwatch equipped with security features

Quote about RDM/RSM: "Precision in research data management is as crucial as in coding for security. One flaw, and the system's integrity could be compromised."

Free Time Activities: Engages in cybersecurity meetups, guest lectures at tech events, and maintains a security-focused vlog.

Interests: Developing ethical hacking courses, AI for threat detection, and is an enthusiast of classical music and literature.

Goals for Work/Academic Life: Aims to elevate the standard of cybersecurity measures in Germany and the EU, advocate for stronger data protection laws, and mentor the next generation of security experts.

Memberships:

- German Informatics Society (GI)
- Network for Women in Computer Science (Frauencomputernetz)
- European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO)

Professional Positions:

1. 2022 - Present: Cybersecurity Lead, Cybersecurity Research Group, Technical University of Munich - Focusing on next-generation encryption technologies.
2. 2019 - 2022: Senior Security Analyst, ProSecure GmbH, Berlin - Developed cybersecurity strategies for corporate clients.
3. 2016 - 2019: IT Security Consultant, CyberProtect AG, Frankfurt - Specialized in risk assessment and security solutions for the finance sector.
- 1.

Intersection with RD/SM:

Reread your quote: Dr. Alex Kim's experiences in RDM/SM led her to emphasize the defensive role of data management in cybersecurity. Her career has included:

- **Success (✓):** Successfully thwarted a major cyber-attack on her university's research data servers by implementing a cutting-edge encryption protocol.
- **Learning Experience (X):** Overlooked a small flaw in an otherwise robust security system, which led to a minor data leak. This experience reinforced her commitment to thoroughness in RDM.

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM?

- Dr. Kim is striving to integrate best practices in RDM into the core of cybersecurity operations, ensuring that every team member is equipped with the knowledge and tools to protect sensitive data.
- She aims to teach and mentor students and staff about the importance of RDM, advocating for its role in protecting academic integrity.
- She is leading initiatives to create secure services for data sharing and collaboration across research institutions, enhancing the security infrastructure for collective defense against cyber threats.

What could help to address this person in her RD/SM?

- Ongoing professional development opportunities in the latest RDM and cybersecurity trends.
- Investment in state-of-the-art security software that aligns with the latest RDM standards.
- Collaboration with international cybersecurity experts to develop a global RDM framework.

Anything else to say about the persona?

- Dr. Kim is known for her proactive approach to RDM, often running simulations and training exercises to prepare for various data breach scenarios.
- She has a philosophy of 'security through education', believing that empowering individuals with knowledge is key to a stronger, more resilient cybersecurity posture.
- Outside of her technical work, she actively participates in policy discussions to shape the future of cybersecurity and data protection legislation.

Cluster Name: Support Structures

Personas of Persons in Academia

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your consortia. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	Jenny Wong	Gender	female
Field of Study	Computational Biology	Degree	Dr.
Research Disc.	Eco-system development	Position	Team Lead
Affiliation	RWTH Aachen		

	Hair	black
	Skin	pale
	Fashion Style	casual business
	Glasses/contact lenses	glasses
	Jewellery	ear rings
	Wearables	fitbit
	Quote about RDM/RSM	This ensures/creates legal certainty

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

spending time in nature / hiking

Jogging
Growing vegetables on balcony

What are the goals for the work/academic life?

Becoming professor

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

Advisory Board ~~Eifel~~ National Board
Eifel

ISCB (Intl. Society for Computational Biology) Student Chapter

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
2022 - now	PostDoc	RWTH Aachen
2018 - 2021	Ph. D.	Univ. of Cologne
2015 - 2017	Master	Fudan Univ. Shanghai

Intersection with RD/SM

Reread your quote: Which experiences in RD/SM led your person to say this? Are these experiences success (✓) or failure (✗) stories?

Artifact creation: publication of data + analysis SW for
nature journal

✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗

Integration of data from GIS

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM? Integrating good practices into his/her daily life, teach people about, create services, ...?

Consensuing politicians in her role as advisor ~~at~~ National
Park Eifel

What could help to address this person in his RD/SM?

Version management of GIS data
Established meta data formats for GIS data

Anything else to say about the persona?

Cluster Name: Resources

Personas of Persons in Academia

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your cluster. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	<u>John Doe</u>	Gender	<u>Male</u>
Field of Study	<u>Computer Science</u>	Degree	<u>PhD</u>
Research Disc.	<u>AI</u>	Position	<u>Postdoc</u>
Affiliation			

Hair
Skin
Fashion Style
Glasses/contact lenses
Jewellery
Wearables
Quote about RDM/RSM

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

What are the goals for the work/academic life?

- Habilitation - Publishing more papers

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
<u>21 - 23</u>	<u>Postdoc</u>	
<u>19 - 21</u>	<u>Postdoc</u>	
<u>15 - 19</u>	<u>PhD student</u>	

Intersection with RD/SM

Reread your quote: Which experiences in RD/SM led your person to say this? Are these experiences success (✓) or failure (✗) stories?

Pressure and competition in publishing papers is high. It leaves no time for RD/SM	✓	✗
During PhD, tried to build reproducible model, but papers publish took longer than usual	✓	✗
	✓	✗
	✓	✗

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM? Integrating good practices into his/her daily life, teach people about, create services,...

No intrinsic motivation → only tries to comply if there are requirements for RD/SM

What could help to address this person in his RD/SM?

low-level entrance
Easy usage

Anything else to say about the persona?

Politiker; ist Gegenspieler zu Jenny Wong

Cluster Name: Support structures

Personas of Persons in Politics/Industry/Society

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your cluster. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	Marth Frings	Gender	Male
Field of Study	Geography / Sports	Degree	Magister
Profess. Domain	City Council Monschau	Position	Teacher High School
Affiliation			

DRAW ME

Hair colour	
Skin colour	
Fashion Style	
Glasses/contact lenses	
Jewelry	—
Wearables	
Quote about RDM/RSM	I need legal advice first

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

What are the goals for his/her work life?

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
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Intersection with RD/SM

Reread your quote: Which incidents has the person heard about RD/SM? Does the person remember more success (✓) or failure (✗) stories?

✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗

How relevant is RD/SM for the personal or organisational agenda? The person wants to integrate Research Data/Software into a political agenda, use RD/RS in research activities in industry, use results from a standardisation process...?

From the person's point of view: what would support RD/SM?

Anything else to say about the persona?

Name: Dr. Martin Schneider

Gender: Male

Degree: Ph.D. in Computer Science with Data Science specialization

Position: Head of Data Compliance

Field of Study: Computer Science, Data Science

Professional Domain: Automotive Industry Compliance

Affiliation: Autotech Data Systems, Munich, Germany

Hair Colour: Dark brown, kept short

Skin Colour: Medium, often with a light stubble

Fashion Style: Smart-casual with an emphasis on eco-friendly clothing brands

Glasses/Contact Lenses: Sports transition lenses

Jewellery: Titanium band watch with GPS tracking

Wearables: Fitness tracker with NFC for secure payments

Quote about RDM/RSM: "In the interconnected world of automotive data, compliance is not just about following rules; it's about ensuring trust in every byte of data we collect and process."

Free Time Activities: Enjoys developing open-source compliance tools, cycling, and participating in forums on data ethics.

Interests: Passionate about sustainable automotive technologies, big data analytics for smart cities, and privacy in the age of IoT.

Goals for Work/Academic Life: To establish industry-leading standards for location data management in the automotive sector and to spearhead initiatives for global data compliance.

Memberships:

- International Association of Privacy Professionals (IAPP)
- Automotive Data Compliance Board (ADCB)
- German Informatics Society (GI), Special Interest Group on Data Science

Professional Positions:

1. 2023 - Present: Head of Data Compliance, Autotech Data Systems, Munich - Overseeing compliance of location data usage across international markets.
2. 2020 - 2023: Data Science Lead, Mobility Innovations GmbH, Stuttgart - Led the integration of location data services with real-time traffic management systems.
3. 2017 - 2020: Compliance Analyst, CarSecure AG, Berlin - Developed compliance frameworks for autonomous vehicle data.

If there are specific characteristics or details you would like to add or change, please let me know.

Intersection with RD/SM:

Experiences in RDM/SM: Dr. Martin Schneider's career has been a blend of success and learning experiences. His quote reflects his understanding of the importance of trust in data management, which was shaped by:

- **Success (✓):** Development of a compliance framework that was adopted across multiple departments, leading to a significant reduction in data breaches.
- **Learning (X):** Early in his career, he faced a setback when a project ran afoul of GDPR regulations due to poor data handling practices, which taught him the importance of robust RDM protocols.

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM?

- Dr. Schneider is working to integrate state-of-the-art RDM practices into every level of the data lifecycle in the automotive industry.
- He is dedicated to teaching his colleagues about the importance of data compliance, and how it can be implemented without hindering innovation.
- He is also involved in developing services and tools that facilitate secure and compliant data sharing between departments and with external partners.

What could help to address this person in his RD/SM?

- Access to advanced tools for real-time monitoring of data compliance.
- Regular training sessions for staff on new data protection laws and regulations.
- A cross-departmental committee dedicated to discussing and implementing RDM best practices.
- Partnerships with technology providers to stay ahead of the curve in data security and compliance.

Anything else to say about the persona?

- Dr. Schneider is a visionary who believes that compliance should be proactive rather than reactive.
- He advocates for privacy by design, ensuring that all new technologies developed within his company incorporate data protection from the outset.
- His leadership style is collaborative, and he often leads by example, volunteering to test new compliance tools and processes personally.

Dr. Schneider remains a highly respected figure in the intersection of automotive industry and data science, known for his pragmatic approach to solving complex compliance issues while advancing the industry's use of data for innovation. Would you like to add any specific incidents or milestones in his journey?

Cluster Name: Cultural Change

Personas of Persons in Academia

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your cluster. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	<u>Dr. Napoleon Schmidt</u>	Gender	<u>Male</u>
Field of Study	<u>Datenschutz Verwaltung</u>	Degree	<u>PHD</u>
Research Disc.	<u>Data Privacy</u>	Position	<u>CIO</u>
Affiliation	<u>CEO CIO Germany University</u>		

Hair	<u>No hair</u>
Skin	<u>White</u>
Fashion Style	<u>Suit and Tie</u>
Glasses/contact lenses	<u>Glasses</u>
Jewellery	<u>None / Broken ring</u>
Wearables	<u>Apple watch</u>
Quote about RDM/RSM	<u>Always raise the privacy issue, not ready to sign off</u>

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

Watching sherlock holmes with cigar in mouth
Statistics about sports
Winning the Argument

What are the goals for the work/academic life?

Retiring without scandals

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

Shepherd Association

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
	<u>Network officer</u>	
	<u>Network officer</u>	
	<u>CIO</u>	

Cluster Name: Know-How

Personas of Persons in Academia

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your cluster. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	Patricia Becker	Gender	male
Field of Study	Bibliometrics	Degree	PhD
Research Disc.	Humanities	Position	Viz. Mit.
Affiliation	uni (KIT)		

Hair	Brown
Skin	White
Fashion Style	hipster
Glasses/contact lenses	Glasses
Jewellery	-
Wearables	Wear
Quote about RDM/RSM	" better sense " "better compliance"

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

spielt Gitarre

What are the goals for the work/academic life?

Impact on FAIR Data

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

Impact on FA 6/1

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
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Intersection with RD/SM

Reread your quote: Which experiences in RD/SM led your person to say this? Are these experiences success (✓) or failure (✗) stories?

Erkund-Daten konnten für Robotearbeit nicht genutzt werden ✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM? Integrating good practices into his/her daily life, teach people about, create services,...

How to use digital services for data retrieval
Raise awareness on data usage compliance

What could help to address this person in his RD/SM?

Schulungsmaterial / Guidelines

Anything else to say about the persona?

Personas of Persons in Academia

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your cluster. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	Peter Øst doc	Gender	
Field of Study	APC	Degree	PhD
Research Disc.	CS	Position	Postdoc
Affiliation	TU Bielefeld		

	Hair	Trimmed Dark Brown + Silver
	Skin	Fair, Healthy / Pale
	Fashion Style	Practical, Sweater
	Glasses/contact lenses	Rectangular, thin-framed
	Jewellery	Smart Earring
	Wearables	Smart Watch
	Quote about RDM/RSM	It distracts me from my research.

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

Kerbal Space Program (on the cluster)

What are the goals for the work/academic life?

Permanent position

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

ACM, IEEE, GI, Peter

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
irregular	working student	Startup (failed)
2017-2022	PhD student	Uni
2022-	Postdoc	Uni

Intersection with RD/SM

Reread your quote: Which experiences in RD/SM led your person to say this? Are these experiences success (✓) or failure (✗) stories?

Deadline driven Paper development	✓	✗
Large amount of accumulated unsorted data	✓	✗
	✓	✗
	✓	✗

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM? Integrating good practices into his/her daily life, teach people about, create services, ...?

Sort it later (Quote still fine)
Find hidden secrets in data (energy consumption of individual TCP packets)

What could help to address this person in his RD/SM?

Guarantees about storage capabilities of RSM system
→ data amount → Measurement (organization/secret)
→ group pressure
→ compliance (conferences)

Anything else to say about the persona?

Data hoarder

Cluster Name: Impact

Personas of Persons in Academia

Imagine being part of your Stakeholder cluster. In the following questionnaire you can create a fictional character. Please be as detailed as possible to create realistic impression of a person which belongs to your cluster. This persona will be utilized to develop and evaluate activities for our consortia. So, any detail or well written description will help to have a better understanding of the requirements.

Background information

Name	Wim	Gender	m.
Field of Study	Digital Humanities (Media), BA in Anglistik Geschichte	Degree	BA
Research Disc.		Position	MA student
Affiliation	Wuppertal		

Hair	
Skin	
Fashion Style	
Glasses/contact lenses	Ja, Brille
Jewellery	Rings
Wearables	Smartwatch
Quote about RDM/RSM	Publishing research data can also be materially rewarding

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?

Wetter

What are the goals for the work/academic life?

Academic career -> MA -> PhD -> Professorship in 8 years

Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)

List at least 3 of the most recent professional positions

From ... to ...	Job Description	Affiliation
2021 - 2023	Hilfskraft	University library
2023 - ...	Hilfskraft, Research project	Institute

Intersection with RD/SM

Reread your quote: Which experiences in RD/SM led your person to say this? Are these experiences success (✓) or failure (✗) stories?

Job als Wiss. HK durch Erfahrung in RD-Positionen ✓ | ✗
Hochqualitative RD zu stellen ist auch viel Arbeit ✓ | ✗
Früheren Veröffentlichung von RD kann sichtbar (Prof. Muchhats nicht gesehen) ✓ | ✗
✓ | ✗

What is the person trying to do with RD/RSM? Integrating good practices into his/her daily life, teach people about, create services, ...?

Veröffentlichen als Service im Projekt
Experte für RD-Maßnahmen in der Gruppe
Diversity Struktur ins Chaos

What could help to address this person in his RD/SM?

Gleichgesinnte finden
Service-Infrastruktur anbieten

Anything else to say about the persona?

Empty lined area for additional notes.